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The Role of Cities in Social Life during the Khanate Period (On the Example of the Bukhara Emirate)

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***Annotation:** This article examines the cities that functioned during the Khanate period and their importance for the comprehensive development of the population of their state. It is known that the role of cities in the political, socio-economic and cultural life of society was of varying degrees. In most cases, cities are characterized by the formation and development of cities in places with favorable geographical and topographical conditions. In addition, the formation and development of cities is determined by the peaceful coexistence of states and the rational policy of rulers. These aspects were studied in the article based on the analysis of available sources and literature.*

***Keywords:** Bukhara Khanate-Emirate, Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Termez, Karshi, Khasan Khoja Nisari, Anthony Jenkinson, Sea of Secrets, Mukhammad Salikh, Master Mawlana Moili, Caravanserai of the Money Changers, P. I. Demezov, Khafiz Tanish Bukhari.*

INTRODUCTION

The role of cities in the political, socio-economic and cultural life of the Uzbek khanates formed in Central Asia was unparalleled. This period covers the period from the 16th century to the second half of the 19th century and is called the Late Middle Ages. Before describing in detail the role of cities in the life of society during this period, it is necessary to dwell briefly on their formation.

Research shows that one of the main factors in the formation of cities goes back to the socio-economic basis, which is characterized by the separation of crafts as an independent branch from agriculture, which was the main occupation of the local population. As a result of this division, the population settled in different parts of the countries of Central Asia, depending on the types of occupations they were engaged in. Political, social and economic centers were formed on the basis of certain estates of feudal lords. Typically, the settlements of local rulers and landowners located in these centers were

occupied by the population engaged in trade and crafts. As a result of the development of socio-economic life, their borders expanded further in the territory they occupied. As a result, cities were formed on the basis of such centers, which over the centuries went through stages and crises in their development [Agzamova G.A., P.118-124.].

MAIN PART

During the last Middle Ages, there were many cities on the territory of the Bukhara Khanate, which were different in size, population, location, level of development of socio-economic life, and differed from each other in some aspects of cultural development. Such cities include Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Termez, Karshi and many other centers, the origins of which go back to ancient times.

Some sources, although scanty, have preserved some information about the size of these cities. In particular, Khasankhoja Nisari, who lived in the 16th century, wrote about Bukhara: "The distance of the land of Bukhara is twelve by twelve farsangs" [Khasankhoja Nisari, P.72].

Some information about the size of Central Asian cities compared to their time has been preserved in other sources. In particular, it is noteworthy that the Englishman Anthony Jenkinson, a representative of the "Moscow Trading Company", who had seen many European cities and visited a number of cities of Moscow and the Russian state, wrote about Bukhara in the late 50s of the 16th century: "The city is very large." [Agzamova G.A., P. 118-124.]

The role of cities in the political, socio-economic and cultural life of society was of varying degrees. In most cases, cities are characterized by the formation and development of their development in places with favorable geographical and topographical conditions. Such cities include Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Karshi, and others, which were major political, trade, economic, and cultural centers of the Middle Ages. The 17th-century author Mahmud ibn Vali, writing about Samarkand, specifically notes the following: "Samarkand is one of the most beautiful and prosperous cities in the world due to its vast territories, good climate, and other means of excellence and grandeur" [Makhmud Ibn Vali., P.166].

The above cities were political centers that embodied the main social forces existing in the Bukhara Khanate. Political forces such as the Supreme Ruler - the khan, representatives of the ruling dynasty, various officials, and priests were concentrated in them, and all domestic and foreign policy was controlled from these centers. They developed as the capital city - the main trade, economic and cultural centers of the country.

The stable political and socio-economic situation played an important role in the development of the cities of the late Middle Ages. During this period, the turbulent, contradictory processes that took place in the states formed in the territory of Central Asia - the Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand khanates - led to many imbalances in political, socio-economic life. During the period of political unrest and internecine wars, cities and life in them experienced a deep crisis. Conflicts and wars between individuals claiming control over a particular province or city often ended with the siege of the capital city or fortress of the province. This struggle between rulers led to a sharp deterioration in the socio-economic life of the besieged city. This situation often led to the disruption of economic relations between cities and villages, and life in them fell into a state of temporary stagnation. Usually, within a few months, socio-economic life in cities under siege collapsed, the standard of living of their inhabitants dropped significantly, and famine often occurred.

Cities played a special role in the struggle for power between representatives of the ruling dynasties and in the system of other political events. They passed from hand to hand in the years of weakening

of the centralized state and the rise of separatist sentiments among some local rulers. As a result of this process, the cities and their socio-economic life were disrupted, and the standard of living of the population deteriorated sharply. As a vivid example of this, it is worth recalling the continuous struggles between Muhammad Shaybani Khan and Timuridzade Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur at the beginning of the 16th century. As a result of one of such struggles in 1500-1501, the historian Muhammad Salih noted the following about the situation that arose in the capital city of Samarkand: "Many died because of the external fruit, and the internal people died because of the internal hunger. The external fruit was abundant, and the internal people were dying of hunger" [Khafiz Tanish Bukhari., P.232].

When determining the place of cities in medieval society, it is important to note that they were political and administrative centers. A unique system of governance was formed in cities and their subordinate regions, which were administered by governors. The city administration officials, the qazi and rais, were subordinate to them. These individuals tried to maintain the political, socio-economic life of the city and the lifestyle of the city's residents in a harmonious manner.

Cities were centers where various types of society of the late Middle Ages lived and worked: officials, people of various professions, merchants, scholars, writers and poets, etc., as well as large landowners. These individuals, who owned large land and received incalculable income from them, often spent their money on purchasing real estate. They usually bought and owned markets, caravanserais, shops and other types of real estate and increased their wealth by receiving income from them. We can observe this from the documents of the sheikhs of Joibor, who held a significant position in the political and socio-economic life of the Bukhara Khanate in the 16th-17th centuries, in which the purchase and sale of land and various real estate was formalized. In particular, in one of them (1559), the list of properties in Bukhara mentions a caravanserai and a land plot endowed by the late emir Latif Mirak. [Agzamova G.A., P.118-124.] The medieval scholar R. G. Mukminova points to this way of living of representatives of large landowners in cities and their active participation in socio-economic life as a distinguishing feature of the cities of Central Asia in the late Middle Ages from the cities of Western Europe in certain periods of historical development [Mukminova R.G. , P.130.]. Indeed, the development of Europe in the Middle Ages shows that large feudal lords in them usually did not live in cities, but in manors on land plots that they owned.

In determining the place of late medieval cities in social life, their role as centers of crafts and trade is of particular interest. Cities were usually inhabited by people of various professions. The diversity of occupations of craftsmen can be judged on the basis of evidence dating back to the end of the 16th century. In the qazi documents for Samarkand alone, it is noted that in the 16th century there were 61 types of crafts in the city, among which were cloth weavers (bofandagon), scarf weavers (chahorgulbafon), turban weavers (futabafon), dyers (sabbagon), degreasers (akhangaron), potters (kulolgaron), knife makers (kordgaron), paper makers (kaghazgaron), etc. The products they created satisfied the needs not only of the city dwellers, but also of neighboring villages, other cities and regions, and the inhabitants of the neighboring steppes. The popularity of the products created by the city's craftsmen was widespread in other countries, and the words of the 16th-century historian Hasankhoja Nisari clearly indicate this. Writing about the Bukhara craftsman-master Manlono Moili Sirraj, he notes the following: "He was a man whose fame spread throughout the city and was the only one of his time in his time. The sirraj (light) of the old sirrajs was illuminated by the beauty of his workshop. Merchants took the ornate saddles and harnesses made by Mavlano Moili to the Bulgars and China, where they were praised as excellent examples"[Khasankhoja Nisari., P. 80.].

The sale of various products created by urban artisans required the expansion of internal and external trade and the system of trade and economic structures - markets, shops, caravanserais. This interdependence between crafts and trade led to the further development of the activities of merchants, the strengthening of social stratification between artisans and merchants, and the active involvement of representatives of other social strata of the population in trade processes. In particular, it is clear from the documents of the sheikhs of Joibor of the 16th century that one of the shops, which were considered trade and craft establishments in Bukhara, belonged to Mufti Mavlano Muhammad Amin, one of the baths to Amir Abduali, three shops specializing in making and selling armor to the brothers-emirs - Mirza Mashhadi and Mirza Ulugbek, and the palace known as the "Caravan-Palace of the Moneychangers" belonged to Amir Tinkilich oglu Mirza Bogy [Khafiz Tanish Bukhari., P. 123.]. We can also observe evidence from other periods and in other cities that representatives of different classes of the city's inhabitants were actively engaged in trade. This situation led to a change in the social composition of the city's population during the construction period, significant results in the property stratification of urban society, and became one of the main factors of economic development.

It is worth noting that cities were the centers of material support for the representatives of the ruling circle. The above-mentioned Anthony Jenkinson noted in 1558: "The king of Bukhara has neither great power nor wealth; his income is very small; he lives mainly at the expense of the city"[Декинсон А., P.182]. The fact that the representatives of the upper class, who lived at the expense of income received from the inhabitants of cities and villages in the form of various taxes, fell into a helpless situation during times of political unrest and economic crises can also be seen from the following words of the 18th century author - Florio Beneveni, Peter I's ambassador to Central Asia.

The Russian ambassador noted that in the 20s of the 18th century, "the Khan (Khan of Bukhara) himself lost a large half of his camels, horses and cattle" and was forced to buy them for money [Usmonov K..., P. 129.]. This situation is also clearly observed in the example of other Central Asian states - the cities of Khiva and the Kokand Khanate.

Cities were also centers that gave a positive impetus to the development of economic life in their suburbs and villages. Products grown in the suburbs and villages - cotton, flax, grain, rice, tobacco, livestock products and many other types of products - were in great demand in the cities. Some of these products were raw materials for urban artisans. The villagers were one of the main consumers of various things made by artisans. This had a positive impact on the development of many types of crafts, in particular, those specialized in satisfying rural needs. Thus, the interaction that emerged between the leading sector of the urban economy - handicrafts - and the villages was the main factor that ensured, on the one hand, economic development in the countryside, and on the other hand, the development of the urban economy.

The development of socio-economic life and the development of economic relations in the Uzbek khanates of Central Asia increased the importance of some cities as centers that regulated the economic life and directed the development of cities. Such cities include Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand, Tashkent. At the same time, specialization of some cities in the creation of certain types of products and the supply of raw materials is also observed. The information written by the Russian P. I. Demezov in 1834 shows that the importance of the city of Bukhara as a center of economic life was incomparable. In particular, rice and pomegranates from Shakhrisabz, tobacco from Karshi, unprocessed "yellow silk" from Kukan, rice from the vicinity of Kokand and Khujand, a large amount of horse, cattle and camel skins, and semi-silk striped fabrics from Khiva were brought to the city and exchanged [History of Uzbek statehood: (from the earliest times to the Russian invasion), P.178.].

In determining the place of cities in the life of late medieval society, it is necessary to give special importance to their role as political, trade, economic and cultural centers connecting people from other cities in the country, villages, neighboring countries, steppes and distant foreign countries. The capital and other cities, which were major centers of political life, were often visited by ambassadors and travelers from near and far countries. In addition, large centers were considered areas where merchants from other cities, steppes and various countries came and stopped and traded their products. Local merchants also loaded their goods into caravans and sent them to distant and near places. It is worth emphasizing that the location of cities on convenient caravan routes played an important role in their transformation into transit trade centers and their economic development.

Such cities include the large cities of the late Middle Ages - Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, Karshi, Kokand, Andijan. Along with Tashkent, Khiva can also be included, which was connected by many caravan routes. From the Khiva region there were routes leading to Bukhara, Iran, the Moscow state (later Russia), the Caucasus, Rum (Turkey) and through it to the pilgrimage. The following message of the historian Abulghazi is noteworthy in this regard. He notes the following about the Bukhara merchants who went to Rum: "... Khoji Kutas came to Khevak at the head of many pilgrims and caravans" [Abulghazi, P.151.].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Representatives of neighboring cities, near and far countries, and steppe people came to the cities of Central Asia for trade, sometimes staying here for many years. In addition, representatives of various peoples who came as a result of wars also lived in the cities. Kazakhs, Turkmens, Russians, Tatars, Indians, Afghans, Iranians, and Yadis who came and settled in the large cities of Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, and Samarkand were engaged in various branches of trade and crafts, making a significant contribution to the socio-economic development of these centers.

The townspeople, who had different religious views, social backgrounds, and professions, united as one and defended their cities during the difficult periods of historical development - political imbalances and mutual wars. The following words of the 16th-century historian Hafiz Tanish Bukhari about the siege of Bukhara are noteworthy. He writes: "The people of the fortress prepared to resist the enemy, to the valley of heroism. In fact, this people was a unique, resolute and wise people in courage and bravery. There were no equals or likes in fearlessness and determination, militancy and heroism" [Hafiz Tanish Bukhari, P.123]. We can observe this situation in the example of the people of other cities as well.

Women played a significant role in the development of beautiful and prosperous cities, as well as in the stability of socio-economic life. From some information, which is very rare in the sources of that time, it became clear that women owned large real estate in cities - courtyards, shops, etc., were engaged in various types of crafts and trade. They also made a significant contribution to achievements in the cultural and household spheres. Finally, the situation and conditions in the medieval Central Asian cities led to the discovery of women's opportunities, abilities and talents and their prosperity. Women, with their modest labor, contributed to the city's economy and its socio-cultural prosperity.

Cities were considered cultural centers where the main scientific forces, creators of monuments of spiritual and artistic culture settled. Many secular and religious buildings were built in them - bazaars and their types with specific names - carpets, toks, chakhorsuks, caravanserais, mosques, madrasas, khanaqas. The construction of such buildings required skilled slaves, talented craftsmen and builders, and skilled architects. Large and small cities of Central Asia acquired a beautiful and colorful appearance mainly due to the labor of local or immigrant craftsmen.

CONCLUSION

Cities were also centers of enlightenment and science. Other cities, villages, neighboring countries, steppes and distant foreign countries, scholars, jurists, and people from various social strata who aspired to enlightenment and sought knowledge were always eager to visit such centers. The following information from the 16th century historian Kamoliddin Binoi is noteworthy in this regard. According to Muarrih, long before the conquest of the lands of the Timurid state in Central Asia, Muhammad Shaybani Khan, the future supreme ruler of Movaraunnahr and the founder of the Shaybani dynasty, "...taught the science of recitation in Bukhara for two years"[Kamaluddin Binai, P. 103].

Thus, the role of cities in social life is multifaceted, and their study allows us to correctly understand and interpret the reality of the late Middle Ages, and shows that the role of cities in the development of political, socio-economic and cultural life in the Central Asian khanates is incomparable. In addition, determining the place of cities in the life of late medieval society allows us to study the life of Central Asian cities in detail, showing the existence of a number of general and specific features characteristic of their development during the period under consideration.

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